

DFT Study of Dissociative Adsorption of Hydrogen Sulfide on Cu(111) and Au(111)

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Density functional theory (DFT) is used to investigate the reaction pathways for H₂S adsorption on Au(111) and Cu(111) at low coverage as well as the full decomposition of H₂S on Cu(111). On both surfaces, a weakly bonded molecular state is found with the S atom bond on top sites being molecular adsorption, a nonactivated process. The H–SH dissociation process is endothermic on Au(111), and all reaction pathways present high activation energy barriers which explains the extremely low dissociation probability of H₂S on defect-free Au(111) estimated from experiments. This scenario slightly changes for H₂S/Cu(111): (i) dissociated configurations are energetically more favorable than the molecular state and (ii) the H–SH bond cleavage process presents a relatively small activation energy barrier. This is not inconsistent with low but nonzero reactive sticking probability of thermal H₂S molecules reported in experiments. The complete energy profile for the H₂S adsorption and full decomposition is compatible with the accumulation of S-adatoms observed experimentally.

Introduction

The study of H₂S adsorption on Au and Cu surfaces is of interest due to various reasons. On one hand, HSH is the simplest sulfur containing molecule which might be used as a benchmark model system to investigate the adsorption dynamics of methanethiol (HSR with R=CH₃)¹ and the formation of self-assembled monolayers (SAMs) on metal surfaces.^{2,3} Though replacing the CH₃ group by an H-atom might seem an oversimplification at a first sight, it has been found that the global energetics (i.e., the difference between the energy of reactive and products) of H–SH and H–SCH₃ dissociation on Au(111) are very similar.⁴ On the other hand, in fuel-based compounds, H₂S is a common impurity that provokes very easily (at ppm levels) the poisoning of Cu-based catalysts due to the formation of S overlayers produced by H₂S decomposition.

Experimentally, adsorption of H₂S on Au(111) and Cu(111) has been studied using temperature-programmed desorption (TPD), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), Auger electron spectroscopy (AES), and low energy electron diffraction (LEED) techniques.^{5,6} On both surfaces, a weakly bound molecular state has been identified at low surface temperatures (below ~125 K). On Cu(111), it has been estimated a small dissociative adsorption probability of H₂S (~0.057 at room temperature, decreasing when the surface temperature increases), and the molecularly adsorbed state of H₂S was assumed to act as a precursor for H–SH

dissociation. The H₂S reactive adsorption probability on Au(111) is much smaller than that on Cu(111),⁵ as expected from the deeper d-band center of Au.⁷ The increase of surface temperature above 100 K only provokes the desorption of the H₂S molecules, and the formation of an atomic S overlayer on defect-free Au(111) requires extremely high exposures or the use of electron beams to induce dissociation.

The adsorption of H₂S on Au(111) and Cu(111) has also been explored theoretically (see refs 4, 8, and 9). The adsorption geometries and energies for the molecular and dissociative states of H₂S have been investigated using density functional theory (DFT) calculations. However, the reaction pathways through which the H₂S molecule decomposes first into H + HS and then into H + H + S have been largely less explored. The knowledge of reaction pathways and the corresponding activation energy barriers are crucial to contrast with theory, the scenario coming out from the available experimental data.

In this work, we present a theoretical study of the interaction of H₂S with clean and defect-free Au(111) and Cu(111) based on DFT calculations. We investigate some reaction pathways for the H–SH bond cleavage on both surfaces. For Cu(111), that presents a higher reactivity, we also explore a reaction pathway for the full decomposition of H₂S. In the case of Au(111), we compare the most favorable reaction pathway we obtain for H–SH bond breaking with the one that was previously determined for the shortest thiol HSCH₃.¹⁰ This allows us to bring some light to the influence of the alkyl chain on the reactive adsorption of the shortest alkanethiols.

The paper is organized as follows. In section II, we summarize the methods employed in our calculations. In section III, we present the main results of our study. First, we briefly summarize some results for bulk Au and Cu as well as for H₂S in vacuum. We then describe the local minima of the PES which are associated to molecularly adsorbed and dissociated states (MAS and DS)

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of H₂S on both Au(111) and Cu(111). Finally, we analyze two possible pathways for the dissociation reaction [(H₂S)_{ads} → H_{ads} + (SH)_{ads}] on both surfaces as well the energetics for the full decomposition of H₂S on Cu(111). Section IV summarizes the conclusions of our study.

Methods

Total energies of H₂S interacting with Au(111) and Cu(111) have been investigated using DFT within the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) proposed by Perdew and Wang (usually called PW91) to account for electronic exchange and correlation.¹¹ The one-electron Kohn–Sham orbitals are expanded in a plane wave basis set, and electron–ion interactions are described through the ultrasoft pseudopotentials¹² developed by Kresse and Hafner.¹³ The Au(111) and Cu(111) surfaces were represented using the slab–supercell approach.¹⁴ In this work, we are interested in adsorption at low coverages. Accordingly, all the calculations have been carried out with a single molecule within a 3 × 3 cell (i.e., at coverage, $\theta = 1/9$) to avoid lateral interactions. The effect of the 22 × $\sqrt{3}$ herringbone reconstruction of Au(111) is not taken into account. To model both surfaces, we have used three-layer slabs (a reasonable compromise between accuracy and computational cost)⁴ and a vacuum space of ~ 21 Å between slabs. The energy cutoffs employed for Au and Cu were 270 and 300 eV, respectively. Electron smearing was introduced following the Methfessel–Paxton technique¹⁵ with $N = 1$ and $\sigma = 0.2$ eV, and the energies were extrapolated to 0 K. All calculations were spin-restricted and have been performed with the Vienna Ab-initio Simulation Package (VASP).^{16–19}

Geometry optimizations to locate local minima of the molecule–surface potential energy surface (e.g., molecular and dissociative adsorbed states) were done using both the gradient-conjugate and quasi-Newton methods. The search of the most favorable dissociation pathways was carried out using the adaptive nudged elastic band approximation (ANEBA) (see refs 20, 21, and references therein). For the configuration with the largest energy along the dissociation pathway obtained from each fully converged ANEBA calculation, we have (i) computed the eigenvalues of the Hessian matrix of the potential energy surface (PES) and (ii) performed full geometry optimization starting from its two nearest configurations. For all the possible *transition states* (TS) reported in this work, we have found only one imaginary frequency, and the full geometry optimizations starting from its back and forward nearest configurations (along the reaction path) ended in a nondissociated and dissociated state, respectively. The latter tests show unambiguously that the highest energy configurations obtained for each reaction pathway investigated correspond to a true saddle point of the full-dimensional PES. The procedure employed in this work to locate possible TS is basically the same as the one described in ref 10. In this work, all the calculations involving geometry optimizations were carried out using a 3 × 3 × 1 Monkhorst–Pack²² k-point mesh. However, the total energies reported for the most relevant configurations so obtained have been computed using a denser 7 × 7 × 1 k-point mesh. Except otherwise stated, throughout this work the reference energy level $E = 0$ is defined as the energy of the H₂S molecule in its equilibrium geometry far from the surface where the molecule–surface interaction vanishes. The adsorption sites of H₂S and the HS group are associated to the position of the S-atom on the surface.

Results and Discussion

Bulk Metals and H₂S in Vacuum. The calculated lattice constants for Au and Cu bulk are, respectively, $a_{\text{Au}}^{\text{calc}} = 3.63$ Å and $a_{\text{Cu}}^{\text{calc}} = 4.18$ Å, in good agreement with the experimental values: $a_{\text{Cu}}^{\text{exp}} = 3.61$ Å and $a_{\text{Au}}^{\text{exp}} = 4.08$ Å.²³ The calculated bond length and bond angle of the H₂S molecule in vacuum are $r_{\text{S-H}}^{\text{calc}} = 1.348$ Å and $\theta^{\text{calc}} = 91.77^\circ$, respectively, in excellent agreement with the experimental data: $r_{\text{S-H}}^{\text{exp}} = 1.328$ Å and $\theta^{\text{exp}} = 92.2^\circ$.²⁴

Molecular and Dissociated States of H₂S on Au(111) and Cu(111). The existence of a molecularly adsorbed state of H₂S on both Au(111) and Cu(111), stable at low surface temperatures (below ≈ 125 K), is well established from TPD and XPS experiments.^{5,6} From our DFT calculations, molecular adsorption is a nonactivated process. A full geometry optimization starting from H₂S far (~ 4 – 5 Å) from both surfaces always ends with H₂S molecularly adsorbed ~ 2.5 – 2.8 Å above the surface topmost layer. We have explored various possible high- and low-symmetry adsorption sites. For both surfaces, we have found a preference for molecular adsorption with the S-atom on top sites. In what follows, this on-top lowest energy molecular state will be referred to as the molecular adsorbed state (MAS). In the MAS, the H₂S molecule lies almost parallel to the surface; on Au(111) and on Cu(111), the angle between the molecular plane normal and the surface normal is 6° and 13° , respectively. The distance between the S-atom and the nearest Au (Cu) atom is $d_{\text{S-Au}} = 2.80$ Å ($d_{\text{S-Cu}} = 2.51$ Å). The H–S distances and the H–S–H angle are barely changed with respect to the values in vacuum. These geometries obtained are very similar to the ones reported in ref 9. The energy of the MAS for Au(111) and Cu(111) are very close to each other: $E_{\text{Au}}^{\text{MAS}} = -0.21$ eV and $E_{\text{Cu}}^{\text{MAS}} = -0.23$ eV, respectively. The computed molecular adsorption energy for H₂S/Au(111), $|E_{\text{Au}}^{\text{MAS}}|$, is slightly smaller than the value predicted from TPD experiments for an initial coverage $\theta \sim 0.1$: $+0.304$ eV.⁵ For H₂S/Cu(111), our result deviates more from the desorption energy roughly estimated from XPS measurements at different surface temperatures (between $+0.375$ and $+0.540$ eV).⁶ Still, the present DFT results are much closer to experiments than the ones ($\sim +0.1$ eV) reported in ref 9. The discrepancy with the latter theoretical results is certainly partially due to the use of a smaller unit cell (higher coverage) considered by Hyman and co-workers.

It is interesting to compare the molecular states of H₂S and HSCH₃¹⁰ on Au(111). Methanethiol adsorbs molecularly on Au(111) below 220 K, and the H–S bond scission only occurs if defect sites are present.^{25,26} HSCH₃ also adsorbs with the S-atom on top; however, the S–Au bond length is shorter ($d_{\text{S-Au}} = 2.65$ Å) and the energy of the molecular state (i.e., -0.35 eV) is lower than that in the case of H₂S. It is very unlikely that such a large energy difference ($\Delta E = -0.21$ eV $+ 0.35$ eV = 0.14 eV) could be due to a stronger van der Waals attraction between the CH₃ group and Au(111). Therefore, the effect of replacing one H-atom (of H₂S) by the CH₃ group seems to have an indirect effect on the S–Au bond. To clarify this point, in Figure 1 we have plotted the density of states projected on the d-orbitals of the topmost layer atoms of the Au(111) surface and the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) of H₂S and HSCH₃ far from the surface. For both molecules, the HOMO is essentially the p_z orbital of the S-atom containing the electron lone pair. This

Figure 1. Density of states projected on the d-orbitals of the topmost layer atoms of the Au(111) surface and the HOMO of H_2S and HSCH_3 far from the surface.

orbital is clearly the one that participates more actively in the molecule–surface bond in the MAS. Figure 1 shows that the HOMO of H_2S has a lower energy than the HOMO of HSCH_3 by 0.5 eV. Thus, following the ideas behind the d-band model,⁷ it is expected that the p_z -derived antibonding level (resulting from the interaction with the Au d-band) for HSCH_3 will be less occupied than for H_2S , producing a higher bonding character of the molecule–surface interaction and a more tightly bound state. This provides an explanation of the larger molecular adsorption energy of HSCH_3 on Au(111).

To determine possible dissociated states (DS), we have performed full geometry optimization for an H-atom and the SH group far from each other within the 3×3 supercell starting from various high- and low-symmetry sites. On both Cu(111) and Au(111), we have found that the SH group preferentially adsorbs with the S-atom close to bridge sites in contrast with atomic S that binds on hollow-fcc sites.²⁷ The distances between the S-atom and the nearest surface atom are $d_{\text{S-Au}} = 2.55 \text{ \AA}$ and $d_{\text{S-Cu}} = 2.32 \text{ \AA}$. The SH group chemisorbs almost flat on the surface being the angle between the S–H bond and the Au(111) (Cu(111)) surface normal, 79° (81.5°). H-atoms occupy hollow-fcc sites at a local H–Au (H–Cu) distance of $d_{\text{H-Au}} = 1.90 \text{ \AA}$ ($d_{\text{H-Cu}} = 1.75 \text{ \AA}$). The energies of the most stable DS on Au(111) and Cu(111) surfaces are 0.19 and -0.86 eV , respectively. Thus, while H_2S dissociation is endothermic on Au(111), it is an exothermic process on Cu(111). Similar results have been found previously in DFT calculations for both H_2S ⁹ and HSCH_3 .^{28,29}

Reaction Pathways for H–SH Bond Cleavage. For both Au(111) and Cu(111) surfaces, we have explored two reaction pathways for the H–SH bond cleavage processes starting from the MAS (Figure 2). In path I, the dissociating (active) H-atom moves first toward the nearest bridge site while it goes to a top site in the path II. In the final (dissociated) state, the SH group and the H-atom are chemisorbed on bridge and hollow-fcc sites, respectively.

The energetics along the resulting dissociation pathways on Au(111) are presented in Figure 3, including plots with the positions of the active H-atom and the SH group for the MAS,

Figure 2. Investigated reaction pathways I (a) and II (b) for the H–SH bond cleavage process. The arrows indicate the motion of the active H and S-atoms.

DS, and saddle points. We have verified that the configurations for which the energy is largest along each path are true saddle points of the PESs. By diagonalizing the corresponding Hessian matrix, for both paths, we have found only one imaginary frequency: 303 cm^{-1} (path I) and 725 cm^{-1} (path II). Moreover, full geometry optimizations starting from configurations close to the saddle point back and forward along the reaction path end in nondissociated and dissociated states, respectively.

The activation energy barriers for both paths are very close to each other: for path I, $E_a^I = 0.72 \text{ eV}$, and for path II, $E_a^{II} = 0.75 \text{ eV}$. Thus, the H–SH bond scission is a highly activated process which explains the extremely low dissociation probability of H_2S on a defect-free Au(111) surface estimated from experiments.⁵

It is important to note that, in both saddle points, the position of the SH group barely changes with respect to that in the MAS. The S-atom is bound to the surface close to a top site, but the distances between the S-atom and its nearest Au surface atom are smaller than those in the MAS: $d_{\text{S-Au}} = 2.49 \text{ \AA}$ (path I) and $d_{\text{S-Au}} = 2.44 \text{ \AA}$ (path II). These smaller distances are due to the fact that, in the saddle points, the H–S bond between the S and the dissociating H-atom is very much weakened compared with the MAS, which entails a stronger S–surface bond.

The results we have obtained for $\text{H}_2\text{S}/\text{Au}(111)$ are (considering geometrical aspects) very similar to the ones recently found for $\text{H-SCH}_3/\text{Au}(111)$.¹⁰ In the latter system, a dissociation pathway very similar to path I (Figure 3a) is also the energetically most favorable one, that is, with the dissociating H-atom close to a bridge site and the SR group close to a top site at the transition state. At the lowest energy saddle point found for $\text{H}_2\text{S}/\text{Au}(111)$, $d_{\text{S-H}} = 2.06 \text{ \AA}$, $d_{\text{H-Au}} = 1.83 \text{ \AA}$, and $d_{\text{S-Au}} = 2.49 \text{ \AA}$, which are all very close to the values found for $\text{HSCH}_3/\text{Au}(111)$: $d_{\text{S-H}} = 2.18 \text{ \AA}$, $d_{\text{H-Au}} = 1.85 \text{ \AA}$, and $d_{\text{S-Au}} = 2.47 \text{ \AA}$. These numbers clearly show a very small effect of the $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$ group in the geometries of the H–SR bond scission process. Still, the activation energy barrier for the H–SH cleavage process is higher than that in the case of methanethiol. This might be linked with the smaller adsorption energy of the MAS in the former case (see above) because, at the transition state, the SR group remains very close to its position in the MAS (for both molecules). To summarize, $\text{H}_2\text{S}/\text{Au}(111)$ appears as a good model system to understand dissociative adsorption of the shortest chain thiols as far as only geometrical aspects are concerned, but the energetics involved are slightly different, apparently due to the more weakly bond MAS.

Figure 4 shows the reaction pathways I and II for the case of $\text{H}_2\text{S}/\text{Cu}(111)$. The situation is now different from the case of Au(111): (i) the H–SH bond cleavage process is energetically much more favorable ($E_a^{II} - E_a^I = 0.51 \text{ eV} - 0.22 \text{ eV} = 0.29 \text{ eV}$) when the H-atom *leaves* the molecule through a bridge site

Figure 3. Energetics along the dissociation pathways (a) I and (b) II on Au(111) including plots with the positions of the active H-atom and the SH group in the MAS, DS, and saddle points.

Figure 4. Same as in Figure 3 but for H₂S/Cu(111).

(path I, in Figure 2) and (ii) the H–SH bond cleavage process is still activated but with a small activation energy barrier of 0.5 eV lower than that for Au(111).

The diagonalization of the Hessian matrix at the highest energy configuration along path I gives rise to only one imaginary frequency (942 cm⁻¹) which confirms that it corresponds to a true saddle point of the multidimensional PES. Moreover, full geometry optimizations starting from configurations close to this one back and forward along the reaction path end in nondissociated and dissociated states, respectively.

The clear preference for dissociation through path I over path II in the case of Cu (in contrast to the case of Au(111)) seems to be connected with the properties of the H-surface interaction potential. First, it is important to note that the heights above the surface where the dissociating H-atom is placed at the saddle

points are close to the optimum heights of an H-atom on the corresponding surface sites in the case of bare surfaces. This is shown in Figure 5 that plots the H/Au(111) and H/Cu(111) potential energy as a function of the H-surface distance, Z_H , on top, bridge, and hollow-fcc sites and where the values of Z_H at the saddle points of paths I and II are labeled by arrows. This suggests that the height above the surface of the dissociating H-atom at the saddle point is strongly influenced by its interaction with the surface with a relatively small effect of the SH group. Second, in the case of Cu(111), H adsorption on a bridge site is more favorable than on a top site by 0.45 eV. This preference is stronger than in the case of Au(111) where adsorption on bridge is more favorable than on top by only 0.17 eV. This provides an explanation of why path I (with the H-atom dissociating through a bridge site) is on Cu(111) clearly more

Figure 5. Potential energy for H on Au(111) and Cu(111) as function of the H-surface distance. Reported energies are relative to the values for an H-atom far from the surfaces obtained in spin-unrestricted calculations.

Figure 6. Energy diagram of the full decomposition of H_2S on Cu(111).

energetically favorable than path II (with the H-atom dissociating through a top site).

To quantify the possible influence of surface relaxation induced by the presence of the adsorbed molecules in the energetics of H_2S adsorption, on Cu(111), we have carried out a few test calculations. We performed a full geometry optimization of the MAS and the DS (including Cu atoms in the two topmost layers), and for the TS we have only allowed surface atoms to relax. We have found a reduction of the energy of all these configurations of ≈ 0.05 eV. Thus, the activated character of the H–SH bond scission process remains unchanged. However, now the activation energy barrier becomes only ≈ 0.15 eV. This relatively weakly activated character of H–SH dissociation is not inconsistent with the low but nonzero reactive sticking probability estimated from experiments in the case of Cu(111)⁶ when it is dosed with thermal energy H_2S molecules. However, a quantitative comparison is beyond the scope of this paper where only the energetics of the adsorption process is considered.

Full Decomposition of H_2S on Cu(111). Due to the higher reactivity of Cu(111), we have also explored a reaction pathway for the full decomposition of H_2S , that is, $\text{HS}_{\text{ads}} + \text{H}_{\text{ads}} \rightarrow \text{H}_{\text{ads}} + \text{H}_{\text{ads}} + \text{S}_{\text{ads}}$. Our results are presented in Figure 6. To verify that the highest energy configuration for H–S bond scission is

a true saddle point of the PES, we have performed Hessian matrix calculations. We have obtained only one imaginary frequency (952 cm^{-1}).

Figure 6 clearly shows that (i) the fully dissociated state (FDS) with two H-atoms and the S-atom placed at hollow-fcc sites is more stable than the DS by 0.34 eV and (ii) the activation energy barrier for the full decomposition reaction is $E_{\text{a}}^{\text{III}} = 0.55$ eV while the activation energy for the reverse reaction is ≈ 1 eV (these activation energy barriers are given with respect to the energy of the DS). On one hand, the fact that the DS is separated from the MAS and FDS by large activation energy barriers makes that the $(\text{SH})_{\text{ads}}$ group can be observed on Cu at low surface temperatures.⁶ On the other hand, thermal fluctuations will irreversibly depopulate this state toward full decomposition because the energy barrier between the DS and the MAS is much higher than that between the DS and the FDS. This scenario is consistent with the accumulation of S-adatoms on Cu(111)⁶ and Cu/MgO(100)³⁰ when the surfaces are exposed to H_2S molecules from a thermal energy source.

Conclusions

In this paper, we have performed density functional theory calculations to investigate possible reaction pathways for H_2S adsorption on Au(111) and Cu(111).

In the case of Au(111), our calculations show that molecular adsorption is nonactivated whereas dissociative adsorption is endothermic and presents a large activation energy barrier. This makes that only molecular adsorption is possible on a perfect Au(111) surface, as it is experimentally observed. The most favorable dissociation pathways for both HSH and HSCH_3 ¹⁰ on Au(111) are very similar: in the transition state, the SR group remains very close to a top site (like in the molecular adsorbed state) and the active H-atom is close to a bridge site. This indicates a moderated effect of the $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$ group in the geometries of the H–SR bond scission process. Still, the activation energy barrier for H–SH bond cleavage is higher than that in the case of methanethiol. This seems to be linked with the smaller molecular adsorption energy of H_2S due to its lower lying HOMO state which entails a higher antibonding character of the bond. Thus, H_2S appears as a good model system to understand dissociative adsorption of HSCH_3 as far as geometrical aspects are concerned, but energetic considerations should be made with caution.

On Cu(111), molecular adsorption of H_2S is also a nonactivated process. Our results predict that H–SH dissociation on Cu(111) is an exothermic activated process that presents a relatively small activation energy barrier (~ 0.15 eV). This is not inconsistent with the (small) nonzero reactive sticking probability observed in experiments with molecules from a thermal energy source. Our calculation also predicts that once the first dissociation has taken place, thermal fluctuation irreversibly produces the full decomposition of H_2S on Cu as found in experiments.

Acknowledgment. This work has been supported by CONICET (Project No. PIP 5248) and ANPCyT (Project No. PICT 33595).

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